

The Impact of *Resign Intention* on Performance of Employees with Loyalty as a Mediation Variable

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Abstract:- The paper purposes to examine the factors which affect employee performance, including: Turnover intention & employee loyalty. In addition, the paper wants to examine the impact of turnover intention on employee loyalty also examine how employee loyalty modulates the impact of employee performance on turnover intention. The participants in this research include amounted to 133 employees of the Infra & EPCC Marketing Department at PT WIKA. The sampling technique used total sampling, where all populations were sampled, but there were limitations to data collection where only 130 questionnaires were collected, so the respondents in this study were 130 employees. The paper SEM-PLS is a descriptive quantitative approach that is employed. The analysis of this study's findings indicates that: Turnover intention has a positive and significant effect on employee loyalty; Turnover intention has no significant effect on employee performance; Employee loyalty has a positive and significant effect on employee performance; Employee loyalty mediates the positive effect of turnover intention on employee performance.

Keywords:- Turnover intention, Employee Loyalty, Employee Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The existence of a company cannot be separated from the role of all employees involved with the company. The progress or slowdown in development experienced by the company lies in how management can form the organization into an appropriate forum for employees to work in order to realize the company's vision and mission. Because in fact, human resources are the most important asset of an organization to be able to achieve organizational goals, so they must be properly maintained by improving the quality of employee performance in order to increase the quality of the business. Every business has human resources tied to it as a need for survival, and these resources help the business achieve its objectives successfully and efficiently. As a result, businesses require trustworthy and competent human resources.

The author interviewed the HRD of PT . WIKA, the results of the interview revealed that there were problems with employee performance, where the results of the performance appraisal for 2019-2021 were not optimal. Based on discussions with HR PT. WIKA that the causes of employee performance are not optimal, one of which is due to high turnover intention and lack of employee loyalty which results in employees not being optimal at work

because they are eager to find another job and are no longer focused on working at PT WIKA. Then the variables that affect employee performance are obtained, including turnover intention and loyalty. Turnover occurs because many employees want to move to another company and for family reasons. The highest data on turnover occurs due to family reasons.

PT. WIKA found problems regarding employee performance, one of which was caused by employee turnover. This The amount of employees that leave the firm in a given period of time, or turnover, is the final truth that the corporation must deal with, while the employee's desire to leave turnover intention refers to individual evaluations regarding the continuation of relationships with organizations that have not been realized in definite actions leaving the organization. Turnover can be in the form of resignation, moving out of the company or the desire to leave the organization generally preceded by employee intentions which are triggered, among others, by low employee loyalty.

Based on the results of the pre-survey about work loyalty at PT. WIKA is synonymous with loyalty which should be carried out under various conditions without conditions and with honesty. The psychological condition that binds employees to PT WIKA, because loyalty is not just physical loyalty which is reflected in how long a person has worked for the company but how much his thoughts, ideas, and dedication have been devoted to the company. Employees at PT. WIKA has less loyalty, this is shown from the pre-survey, a lot of work is done dishonestly and prioritizes personal matters above companies that make performance decline. Employee loyalty is a very important factor to maintain employee performance effectively and efficiently. Disloyal employees tend to show a lack of enthusiasm at work, this will affect employee performance.

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Gaps were still found and from the gap phenomenon from the results of pre-research, this research was conducted to determine the direct and indirect relationship between turnover intention and competency as a mediating factor, the effect of loyalty on employee performance. Several previous studies have explained that loyalty can be a mediating

variable, so in this study loyalty is also considered as a mediating variable. Based on the existence of the problems above, and supported by pre-survey questionnaire data, researchers are interested in taking the research object regarding Then this will Examine the impact of employee loyalty as a mediating factor on the relationship between employee performance and turnover intention at PT WIKA.

II. LITERATUR REVIEW

A. Employee Performance

Due to the many factors involved in evaluating job role behavior, employee performance is a complex organization that is hard to describe or quantify (Atasi et al., 2019). Employee performance, at various levels, is strongly linked to company objectives and stakeholder expectations (Pattnaik & Pattnaik, 2021). Employee behavior, which includes output quality and quantity, attendance at work, helpfulness and accommodativeness, and timeliness of output, is viewed as an indicator of an employee's success (Shahzadi et al., 2014).

Employee performance can be influenced by several factors, including the following: a) Capability and Expertise; b) Personality; c) Work motivation; d) Organizational culture; e) Job satisfaction; f) Work environment; g) Commitment; h) Loyalty.

Robbins and Judge (2015) stated that employee performance has five indicators, namely: a) Quality; b) Quantity; c) Punctuality; d) Effectiveness; and e) Independence.

B. Turnover Intention

According to Melky (2015), an employee's desire to leave their current firm and seek employment elsewhere while still being paid is turnover intention. Turnover intention or the desire to quit is basically the desire or intention to move employees from one workplace to another. Turnover Intention is the level of employee attitude predisposition to search for a new job elsewhere or there is a plan to quit the firm in the upcoming three months, six months, year, and two years.

When an individual has a persistent propensity or desire to leave the organization and be replaced by other employees (Authar, 2019). This opinion shows that turnover intention is the desire to move, not yet in the realization stage, namely moving from one place of work.

According to Belete (2018) there are several factors that can affect turnover intention, namely: a) Leadership Style; b) Demographic Variables; c) Organizational Commitment; d) Organizational Justice; e) Organizational Climate; f) Promotion Opportunity; g) Wages; h) Organizational culture; i) Work Stress; j) Job satisfaction.

Dipboye (2018) suggests that there are three indicators that can be used to measure turnover intention, namely: a) thoughts of stopping; b) The desire to leave; and c) Desire to find another job. According to earlier study, which indicates that an increase in turnover intention will reduce the performance of Rio Syukron Jamal, et.al (2021)

➤ *Hypothesis 1* : It is suspected that there is a negative and significant effect of turnover intention on employee performance.

C. Employee Loyalty

According to Rasmini (2017), work loyalty is a component employed in employee research which includes loyalty to their work, position and organization. This work loyalty is reflected by the availability to defend and protect the organization inside or outside of work from people who are not responsible. Loyalty is a tendency of employees not to change employers because loyalty can impact employees' convenience to work for a company. Loyalty, on the other hand, refers to the employee's sense of attachment to the leader. This can be built psychologically by using methods that are able to capture employees' feelings towards the employer's company (Al-edenat & Alhawamdeh, 2019). This loyalty is reflected in the willingness of employees to protect and defend the organization from disturbances by irresponsible elements both inside and outside of work. Loyalty is reflected in employee performance. If the employee works well, according to regulations and optimally, then it can be assumed that the employee is very loyal to the company; if an employee cannot work properly and optimally, it means that the employee is disloyal to the company (Suhardi et al., 2021).

According to (Siswanto, 2015) employee loyalty indicators have six indicators, namely: a) Compliance with regulations; b) responsibility to the company; c) willingness to cooperate ; d) sense of belonging; e) interpersonal relationships; and f) liking for work. Previous study, which demonstrates that boosting employee loyalty will raise employee performance, supports this. Arisona Chony Ronaldy, et.al (2019).

➤ *Hypothesis 2* : Allegedly there is a positive and significant influence between employee loyalty to employee performance.

Judging from previous research, increased employee loyalty can also be influenced by an increase in turnover intention by Ajimat (2019).

➤ *Hypothesis 3* There is a negative and significant influence between turnover intention on employee loyalty performance.

Furthermore, several studies have shown that employee loyalty can mediate (Sholihin and Ririn, 2021).

➤ *Hypothesis 4* There is a negative influence between turnover intention on employee performance mediated by employee loyalty.

D. Conceptual framework

Based on the research background and theoretical studies above, the conceptual framework of this research can be described as follows:

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a quantitative technique to examine the relationship between employee performance and turnover intention, with employee loyalty serving as a mediating variable. Population is defined as an area that has certain characteristics that have research objects (Sugiyono, 2018). The population in this study is the Department of Infra Marketing and EPCC at PT WIKA, totaling 133 permanent and contract employees. The reason the researcher chose this department was because the sub-optimal work assessment was in the Infra Marketing and EPCC Departments. Determining the number of samples in this study will use total sampling, but due to limitations in filling out questionnaires by respondents, where the data collected is only 130, so 130 employees made up the study's sample. Following data collection, SEM-PLS (Structural Equation Modeling-Partial Least Square) was used to process and evaluate the data. Using the SmartPLS tool, each theory was evaluated.

IV. RESEARCH AND DISCUSSION

A. Profiles of the Respondents

PT. Wijaya Karya began as a subcontracting business. WIKA evolved into a low, medium, and high voltage power network installation contractor in the late 1960s. WIKA diversified their company into home construction and civil contractors in the beginning of the 1970s. Based on Deed No. 110, which was signed in front of Notary Djojo Muljadi, WIKA altered its legal status on December 20, 1972, becoming Limited Liability Company Wijaya Karya (Persero). To carry out its development, WIKA always makes new breakthroughs to evolve becoming a fully integrated infrastructure corporation by creating subsidiaries or divisions like WIKA Beton, WIKA Intrade, and WIKA Realty. Several parties have acknowledged WIKA's development as an integrated infrastructure enterprise. On October 29, 2007, the Indonesia Stock Exchange saw the successful completion of a 35% Initial Public Offering (IPO)

by the firm. Following the IPO, the government of the Republic of Indonesia held 68.4%, while the rest was owned by the public, including employees through the Management Stock Ownership Program (MSOP), Employee Stock Allocation (ESA), and Employee/ Management Stock Option (E/MSOP).

This study the number of respondents based on gender was female, with the highest number being 69 people with a percentage rate of 53%, while male were 61 people with a rate of 47%.

Characteristics of respondents based on age where there are 57 people (43.8%) aged between 20-30 years, 30 people (23.2%) aged between 31-40 years, 29 people (22.2%) aged between 41-50 years, and 14 people (10.8%) were over 50 years old. Respondent data based on age level shows respondents in productive age and the extent of their ability to deal with work or problems that occur.

The number of employees based on educational level, with a large comparison of the characteristics of respondents with a Diploma III level of education totaling 12 people (9.2%), with an S1/Diploma IV education level totaling 103 people (79.2%), while the strata education level two (S2) totaling 15 people (11.6%).

B. Measurements Model (Outer Model)

➤ Outer Model

Testing the convergent validity of each construct indicator. According to Chin in Ghazali (2021) reflection on indicators is assessed based on the correlation between the item score/component score and the construct score calculated with PLS and an indicator is said to have good validation if the loading factor value is greater than 0.70, while a loading factor of 0.50 to 0.60 can be considered sufficient. Based on this criterion, if there is a loading factor below 0.50, it will be dropped from the model.

Table 1 Outer Model Results Summary

	Turnover Intention	Employee Loyalty	Employee Performance
TI 1	0.774		
TI 2	0.735		
TI 3	0.850		
TI 4	0.833		
TI 5	0.780		
TI 6	0.860		
TI 7	0.852		
TI 8	0.770		
LK 2		0.830	
LK 3		0.785	
LK 4		0.800	
LK 5		0.763	
LK 6		0.807	
LK 7		0.840	
LK 8		0.803	
LK 9		0.830	
LK 10		0.873	
KK 1			0.843
KK2			0,753
KK 3			0.709
KK 4			0.870
KK 5			0.804
KK 6			0.831
KK 7			0.806
KK8			0.804
KK 9			0.859
KK10			0.753

According to Figure 4.3 and Table 4.5, which show the outcomes of data processing using SmartPLS, the loading factor values for each indicator are within the required range of 0.70. This demonstrates the validity of the indicators for these variables and their application in the model. The AVE (Average Variance Extractord) value is a metric that may be used to evaluate convergent validity. The minimal AVE value must be 0.5 in order to demonstrate excellent convergent validity, since this indicates that the latent variable can, on average, account for more than half of the variation of its indicators (Ghozali, 2015).

➤ *Validity test*

• *Convergent validity*

Testing for discriminant validity is possible by examining the Fornell-Lacker Criterion. In the Fornell-Lacker Criterion the discriminant validity tested is a problem related to discriminant validity for each construct with correlation values between constructs in the model.

Table 2 Result of Cross Loading Value

Indicator	Turnover Intention	Employee Loyalty	Employee performance	Ket.
TI1	0.774	0.375	0.027	Valid
TI2	0.735	0.364	0.025	Valid
TI3	0.850	0.282	-0.034	Valid
TI4	0.833	0.249	-0.023	Valid
TI5	0.780	0.226	-0.156	Valid
TI6	0.860	0.193	-0.111	Valid
TI7	0.852	0.249	-0.122	Valid
TI8	0.770	0.179	-0.204	Valid
LK2	0.338	0.830	0.278	Valid
LK3	0.330	0.785	0.110	Valid
LK4	0.219	0.800	0.189	Valid
LK5	0.211	0.763	0.274	Valid
LK6	0.293	0.807	0.117	Valid
LK7	0.300	0.840	0.303	Valid
LK8	0.312	0.803	0.314	Valid

LK9	0.211	0.830	0.233	Valid
LK10	0.277	0.873	0.243	Valid
KK1	-0.015	0.276	0.843	Valid
KK2	-0.089	0.153	0.739	Valid
KK3	0.004	0.252	0.709	Valid
KK4	-0.047	0.184	0.870	Valid
KK5	-0.138	0.245	0.804	Valid
KK6	0.006	0.322	0.831	Valid
KK7	-0.105	0.204	0.806	Valid
KK8	-0.135	0.141	0.804	Valid
KK9	-0.051	0.284	0.859	Valid
KK10	-0.078	0.203	0.753	Valid

➤ Reliability test

Composite reliability is an index that shows the extent to which a measuring device is reliable and reliable (Sugiyono, 2018).The reliability test used in this study was done by examining the dependability and consistency of Cronbach's Alpha and Composite dependability values. A construct is deemed credible, according to Ghozali (2015), if the predicted value of Cronbach's Alpha is higher than 0.70 , but for exploratory research above 0.60 it is still acceptable . The composite reliability value must be above 0.70 , while the value of 0.60-0.70 is still acceptable for exploratory research. The findings of the composite reliability and Cronbach's Alpha tests for each research variable are shown below:

Table 3 Reliability Test

Variabel	Composite Reliability	Cronbach's Alpha	AVE	Keterangan
Turnover Intention	0.938	0.925	0.653	Reliabel
Loyalitas Karyawan	0.947	0.937	0,664	Reliabel
Kinerja Karyawan	0.948	0.938	0,645	Reliabel

The test results inshow the composite reliability value for each variable in this study with a value of ≥ 0.70 . The highest composite reliability value is in the employee performance variable of 0.938 and the lowest value is the turnover intention variable of 0.925. It is also known that the value of AVE for all variables has an AVE value > 0.5 . Thus, each variable in the study is valid or meets convergent validity.

The test results for Cronbach's Alpha, the highest value is the employee performance variable of 0.948 and the lowest value is the turnover intention variable of 0.938.

Based on table 4 , the Cronbach's Alpha and composite reliability test results for all variables show a value of > 0.6 . According to Hinton, et . al (2013) put forward four points of reliability which include very good reliability (> 0.90), high reliability (0.70-0.90), moderate reliability (0.50-0.70) and low reliability (low reliability). < 0.50 . So that in this study the reliability is in the very good category because it is above 0.9 .

C. Inner Model

➤ Testing the Coefficient of Determination (R-Square/

Evaluation of the inner model is done by looking at the coefficient of determination. The coefficient of determination aims to measure how far the model's ability to explain the variance of the dependent variable. The value of the coefficient of determination is between 0 and 1. The value of

R^2 explains how much the hypothesized independent variable in the equation is able to explain the dependent variable.

Table 4 R Square

	R Square.	R Square adjusted.
Employee Loyalty	0.119	0.0.112
Employee performance	0.121	0.175

From the table above it can be seen that the R-Square value for the employee loyalty variable is 0.119 which means that 11.9% of the contribution of employee loyalty is influenced by turnover intention, while the remaining 88.1% is explained by other factors. Based on the results of data processing, the R-Square value for the Employee Performance variable is 0.121, which means that 12,1% of the Employee Performance contribution is influenced by employee turnover intention and loyalty, while the remaining 87,9% is explained. by other factors outside the research.

➤ Q-Square .

Predictive Relevance (Q^2) for structural models measures how well the observed values are generated. Predictive Relevance (Q^2) for structural models measures how well the observed values are generated by the model and also the parameter estimates. Applies only to endogenous factor models . Predictive Relevance (Q^2) is greater than 0, in the same way, a Predictive Relevance (Q^2) with 0 or a negative value indicates the model is not relevant to the prediction of a given endogenous factor.

Table 5 Q-square.

	(SSO)	(SSE)	(Q ²) (=1-SSE/SSO)
Turnover Intention	1040.000	1040.000	
Employee Loyalty	1170.000	1080.936	0.074
Employee performance	1300.000	1208.835	0.070

Based on the calculation of predictive relevance (Q²) in Table 6 which shows the value of the employee loyalty variable is 0.126, the value of the Employee Performance variable is 0.036. The value of these two variables is greater than 0 so it can be concluded that the model has a relevant predictive value.

➤ Hypothesis testing

Hypothesis testing utilizes Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) analysis of all smartPLS models. Structural equation modeling of the entire model not only confirms the theory but also explains whether there is a relationship between latent variables or not. The hypothesis is accepted if the t-statistic value is greater than the t-table value, and the hypothesis is rejected or accepted using a probability value if the p-value <=; 0.05.

Hypothesis testing uses a full model structural equation modeling (SEM) analysis with SmartPLS. In a full model, structural equation modeling apart from confirming the theory, also explains whether or not there is a relationship between latent variables. The hypothesis is said to be accepted if the value of the T statistic is greater than the T table and to reject or accept the hypothesis using a probability value, if the P-value <0.05 then Ha will be accepted which means if:

- If the t-statistic value is smaller than the t-table value (t-statistic <1.66) then Ho is accepted and Ha is rejected.
- If the value of the t-statistic is greater than or equal to the t-table (t-statistic > 1.66) then Ho is rejected and Ha is accepted.

Fig 2 Bootstrapping

Table 7 Hypothesis testing

	Original Sampel (O)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistik (O/STDEV)	P Values	Ket.
Turnover Intention (X1) → Loyalitas Karyawan (Y1)	0.345	0.112	3.087	0.002	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Turnover Intention (X1) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	-0.203	0.109	1.864	0.063	Tidak berpengaruh negatif
Loyalitas Karyawan (Y1) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	0.361	0.090	4.019	0.000	Berpengaruh positif dan signifikan
Turnover Intention (X1) → Loyalitas Karyawan (Y1) → Kinerja Karyawan (Y2)	0.125	0.052	2.377	0.018	berpengaruh positif dan signifikan

Sumber: Olah data SmartPLS 3

D. Discussion

➤ *H1* Turnover intention on employee performance . the path coefficient value is -0.203, the t-statistic value is $1.864 > 1.66$) and the P-Values = $0.063 > \alpha = 0.05$. This means that the variable turnover intention has a positive and significant effect on employee performance variables. The hypothesis (H2) in this study which states that "turnover intention has no negative and significant effect on employee performance (Y2)" is rejected.

This means that turnover intention is a variable that does not affect employee performance at PT WIKA employees. In this case employee turnover has no effect on employee performance. This is not in line with the results of research conducted by Rio Syukron Jamal, et.al (2021) which states that turnover intention has no negative and insignificant effect on employee performance. All of this can be caused if what is lived by employees is uncomfortable so that the desire to leave the company grows. However, if employees feel comfortable in the company and there is no desire to leave, it will have a positive impact on the company, so that employee performance will be better.

➤ *H2* Loyalty to employee performance. It is known that the path coefficient value is 0.361, the t-statistic is 4.019 which is 1.66 greater and P-Values = 0.000 is smaller 0.05. This means that the employee loyalty variable has a positive and significant effect on employee performance variables. The research hypothesis (H2) that "employee loyalty has a positive and significant effect on Employee Performance " is accepted. This is consistent with the research by Arisona Chony Ronaldy, et.al (2019), that employee loyalty has an impact on employee performance.

The results of the hypothesis test show that H3 is accepted and it is concluded that employee loyalty has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. This means that employee loyalty is a variable that affects employee performance for employees at PT WIKA. Employee loyalty can creating good employee performance so that employees can work with quality work that meets company standards, work results are always on target so good work loyalty can affect performance employee.

This is in line with the results of research conducted by Arisona Chony Ronaldy, et.al (2019) which states that employee loyalty has a positive and significant effect on employee performance.

➤ *H3* Turnover intention on loyalty. the path coefficient value is 0.345, the t-statistic value is $3.087 > 1.66$) and the P-Values = $0.002 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that the variable turnover intention (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee loyalty variable (Y1).

The results of the hypothesis test show that H3 is rejected and that turnover intention has a positive and significant effect on employee loyalty. This means that turnover intention is a variable that affects employee loyalty to employees at PT WIKA. This is not in line with the results of research conducted by Ajimat (2019) which states the role of organizational commitment in the negative effect of turnover intention on employee loyalty.

➤ *H4* The effect of *turnover intention* on employee performance is mediated by loyalty. the path coefficient value is 0.125, the t-statistic value is $2.377 > 1.66$) and the P-Values = $0.018 < \alpha = 0.05$. This means that the variable turnover intention (X1) has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y2) which is mediated by employee loyalty (Y1). Thus the hypothesis (H4) in this study which states that "turnover intention (X1) has a negative and significant effect on the variable Employee Performance (Y2) which is mediated by employee loyalty (Y1)" is rejected.

This finding implies that employee loyalty mediates the effect of turnover intention on employee performance at PT WIKA. PT WIKA employees want good cooperation between employees. The influence of turnover intention here is positive on employee performance mediated by employee loyalty, so that when employees have no desire to leave the company it will make employees work with high loyalty so that it will create good work results. This is in line with what was stated by Ustadus Sholihin and Ririn Wahyu Arida (2021) which stated that loyalty is capable of mediation.

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study is to determine the significant effect of turnover intention on employee performance with employee loyalty as a mediating variable. Based on the data that has been analyzed using the PLS SEM method, the following conclusions can be drawn:

Turnover intention has a negative and significant effect on employee loyalty at PT WIKA. This means that when turnover intention in a company increases, employee loyalty to their work decreases. So turnover intention is one of the factors that influence employee loyalty. Turnover intention has no significant effect on the performance of PT WIKA's employees. This shows that the higher the employee's desire to leave the company, the higher this is does not affect employee performance WIKA. Employee loyalty has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at PT WIKA. This means that if high employee loyalty can improve good employee performance. Turnover intention has a positive and significant effect on employee performance through employee loyalty to PT WIKA. Thus, if the employee's performance appraisal increases because the employee already has the desire to leave the company, this causes the employee to have high loyalty to his job because he will leave the company and take advantage of the remaining time. so it will produce good results.

This research has several limitations. In this study only analyzes the influence of turnover intention, and employee loyalty which is analyzed as a variable that affects employee performance. In this context, further research may be conducted on other companies or the wider population. Future research should also consider the use of other variables that affect performance

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